

Evaluating Carbon Farming Practices for sustainable soil management in Citrus Cultivation:

E. Nikolaou*¹, F. Charalambous¹, M. Christoforou², S. Dimitriadi¹, S. Efstathiou², M. Eliades¹, D. Hatjimitsis², E. Neophytou¹, G. Papadavid³, M. Stavrinides², M. Tzouvaras¹, I. Varvaris¹, C. Papoutsas¹

¹Eratosthenes Centre of Excellence, Franklin Roosevelt 82, Limassol, Cyprus

²Cyprus University of Technology, Archiepiskopou Kyprianou 30, Limassol, Cyprus

³Agricultural Research Institute, Nicosia, 1516, Cyprus

eirini.nikolaou@eratosthenes.org.cy

Oranges (citrus) stand out as a fruit of global nutritional and consequently commercial importance, serving as a crucial export product for many countries. Their cultivation in Mediterranean climates requires careful management of soil and water resources, where maintaining fertile and healthy soils is vital for ensuring productivity and fruit quality. Carbon sequestration in soils of citrus orchards represents a significant opportunity for climate change mitigation. Research work demonstrates that cover cropping, reduced or no-tillage pruning residue incorporation, and biochar / compost application significantly improve soil quality and can increase carbon sequestration. In addition, both biochar and compost, improve soil properties by increasing Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) and balancing pH, thereby enhancing nutrient availability for plants. These amendments aid in rehabilitating degraded soils, improve aeration and moisture retention, and support extensive root systems, which assist in carbon sequestration. The research team is actively studying innovative solutions for sustainable soil management and carbon sequestration in citrus cultivation.

Keywords: Carbon farming, soil quality, carbon sequestration, citrus cultivation, sustainability

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the ‘EXCELSIOR’: ERATOSTHENES: Excellence Research Centre for Earth Surveillance and Space-Based Monitoring of the Environment H2020 Widespread Teaming project (www.excelsior2020.eu). The ‘EXCELSIOR’ project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 857510, from the Government of the Republic of Cyprus through the Directorate General for the European Programmes, Coordination and Development and the Cyprus University of Technology.

The present work was carried out in the framework of CARBONICA project that has received funding from the Horizon Europe HORIZON-WIDERA-2022 Research and Innovation Actions, under Grant Agreement No 101087233.